

THE ROLE OF SUMMARIZING AS A COGNITIVE READING STRATEGY IN SECOND LANGUAGE ACQUISITION

Sadikova Gulkhayo Ibrokhimjon qizi

moonxsamsung@gmail.com

Doctoral student of Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages

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Abstract. This article discusses the role of summarizing as a cognitive reading strategy in second language acquisition. Understanding academic material is vital for students, and employing effective strategies is crucial in achieving this goal. Among these strategies, reading strategies play a fundamental role. Reading is central to acquiring knowledge, with each individual engaging in a unique interpretive process. Reading strategies aid in improving comprehension, enabling students to understand text accurately and appropriately. Cognitive reading strategies involve mental processes focused on handling information to facilitate learning. Summarizing, a cognitive reading strategy, involves creating a condensed version of new information obtained from listening or reading. It helps students understand the original text more effectively, analyze and evaluate content, and concentrate on crucial details. Summarizing also enhances critical thinking and writing skills, prepares learners for assessments, and facilitates language learning. Two main factors influence summary writing: the presence or absence of the original text and the characteristics of the text. These factors significantly impact the summarization process, affecting the identification of main ideas and selection of relevant information. Summary writing offers numerous advantages for understanding reading passages, making it a valuable strategy for improving comprehension, critical thinking, writing skills, assessment preparation, and language acquisition in second language acquisition contexts.

Key words: *Reading strategies, cognitive reading strategies, reading comprehension, summarizing, summary writing, ESL students, Second Language Acquisition (SLA)*

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada ikkinchi tilni o'zlashtirishda kognitiv o'qish strategiyasi sifatida xulosalash/umumlashtirishning roli muhokama qilinadi. Talabalar uchun o'quv materialini tushunish juda muhim va bu maqsadga erishishda samarali strategiyalarni qo'llash ham katta ahamiyatga ega. Ushbu strategiyalar orasida o'qish strategiyalari asosiy rol o'ynaydi. O'qib tushunish ko'nikmasi ikkinchi tilni o'zlashtirishda markaziy o'rinda turadi va har bir o'rganuvchi matnni

o'ziga xos talqin qilish jarayoni bilan shug'ullanadi. O'qish strategiyalari tushunishni yaxshilashga yordam beradi, o'quvchilarga matnni to'g'ri va chuqur tushunish imkoniyatini oshiradi. Kognitiv o'qish strategiyalari o'rganishni osonlashtirish uchun ma'lumotlarni qayta ishlashga qaratilgan aqliy jarayonlarni o'z ichiga oladi. Xulosalash, kognitiv o'qish strategiyasi tinglash yoki o'qish natijasida olingan yangi ma'lumotlarning ixchamlashtirilgan versiyasini yaratishni o'z ichiga oladi. Bu talabalarga asl matnni yanada samaraliroq tushunishga, mazmunni tahlil qilish va uni baholashga hamda muhim tafsilotlarga diqqatni jamlashga yordam beradi. Xulosa qilish, shuningdek, tanqidiy fikrlash va yozish ko'nikmalarini oshiradi, o'quvchilarni baholashga tayyorlaydi va til o'rganishni osonlashtiradi. Xulosa yozishga ikkita asosiy omil ta'sir qiladi: xulosani bayon tarzda yozayotganda o'quvchining qo'lida asl matnning mavjudligi yoki yo'qligi va matnning xususiyatlari. Ushbu omillar umumlashtirish jarayoniga sezilarli ta'sir ko'rsatadi, asosiy g'oyalarni aniqlash va tegishli ma'umotlarni tanlashga ta'sir qiladi. Xulosa yozish o'qib tushunishda matn bo'laklarini tushunish uchun ko'plab afzalliklarni taqdim etadi, bu uni tushunish, tanqidiy fikrlash, yozish qobiliyatlarini oshirish, baholashga tayyorgarlik ko'rish va ikkinchi tilni o'zlashtirish kontekstlarida tilni o'zlashtirish uchun qimmatli strategiyaga aylantiradi.

Kalit so'zlar: *o'qish strategiyalari, kognitiv o'qish strategiyalari, o'qib tushunish, xulosa qilish, xulosa yozish, ikkinchi tilni o'rganuvchilar, ikkinchi tilni o'zlashtirish*

Effective comprehension of academic material is crucial for students, and employing various strategies is a key to achieving this aim. Among these strategies, a fundamental one is the utilization of reading strategies. Reading serves as the cornerstone of acquiring knowledge, with each individual engaging in a unique interpretive process. (Maarof, N., & Yaacob, M. 2011). This implies that diverse readers adopt distinct approaches in deriving meaning from textual cues.

Reading strategies play a crucial role in improving understanding of texts. Students who have suitable and effective reading strategies use them well to understand the content of the text accurately and appropriately. According to Solé, reading comprehension strategies encompass a series of steps that include setting goals, planning actions to achieve these goals, evaluating progress, and being open to making adjustments if needed. (Solé, I. 2005.) It is imperative to teach these strategies to students if they aim to achieve effective reading comprehension. Garner, on the other hand, characterizes reading strategies as deliberate and

purposeful activities carried out by engaged readers, often to address perceived cognitive challenges and enhance their understanding of the text. (R. Garner, 1987) Therefore, reading strategies involve how readers handle a reading task, the hints they notice in the text, their understanding of the material, and how they react when they find the text challenging to understand. Furthermore, reading strategies are regarded as advanced procedures in which cognitive and metacognitive processes are crucial.

Students must understand their comprehension levels while reading and learn how to identify clues and answer questions in reading comprehension. Cogmen and Saracaloglu found that basic techniques like underlining, taking notes, or highlighting text can assist readers in understanding and recalling the content. (Cogmen, S., & Saracaloglu, A. S., 2009.) William and Burden mentioned that cognitive strategies involve mental processes focused on handling information to facilitate learning, including obtaining, storing, retrieving, and utilizing information. (Williams, M. & R.L. Burden ,1997).

Cognitive reading strategies greatly aid in improving one's reading skills, particularly in understanding texts. When reading, learners typically use different cognitive strategies to comprehend the text. These strategies are crucial for gaining a thorough understanding of the material because learners must not only be aware of their thinking process but also plan and assess their approach. With these strategies, students can effectively answer reading comprehension questions, read autonomously, and retain the information they have read.

The utilization of cognitive strategies can enhance how effectively a learner tackles various learning tasks. These tasks may encompass activities such as recalling and applying information from course materials, forming sentences and paragraphs, revising written work, restating information in one's own words, and organizing information for learning purposes. In a classroom environment where cognitive strategies are implemented, the teacher plays a crucial role in connecting students with the content or skills they need to acquire. This role involves understanding the task at hand and possessing knowledge of effective approaches that can be conveyed to the learner.

Summarizing involves creating a mental, spoken, or written summary of new information obtained from listening or reading. It is a beneficial strategy that helps students understand the original text more effectively and demonstrates their comprehension. Furthermore, the act of summarizing enables students to analyze and evaluate the original text using the knowledge they have acquired.

According to Hays, summarizing is described as a "synthetic strategy" in which students must assess the significance of the information present in the text. (Hays, D.,1989) Likewise, Kamhi-Stein categorizes summarization as an elaboration strategy for tackling intricate learning assignments. (Kamhi-Stein, L.,1993) Summary writers are not solely tasked with synthesizing the content but also with generating a cohesive text that effectively represents the original text by substantial standards (Dole, Duffy, Roehler, & Pearson, 1991, p. 244).

Weinstein and Mayer suggest that the purpose of summarizing is to merge new information with students' existing knowledge. (Weinstein, C. E., & Mayer, R. E. 1986) And they outline four primary objectives of summarization.

- The first aim is to distinguish the main ideas from minor details.
- The second goal is brevity, where summary writers aim to convey the information from the text using as few words as possible.
- The third objective is objectivity due to that, summaries focus on presenting someone else's ideas. Here, writers aim to demonstrate their comprehension of the text rather than responding to the author's ideas.
- Lastly, the fourth goal is accuracy, where writers ensure that the information in the summary remains faithful to the original text.

Consequently, summary writing is a multifaceted task commonly found in academic settings. Contrasting summary writing with other writing tasks, while average writing tasks entail producing content based on a given topic, summary writing involves creating a shortened and condensed version of the original text.

Two main factors influence summary writing: the presence or absence of the original text and the characteristics of that text. (Ashrafzadeh & Nimehchisalem, 2015).

A. The presence or absence of the original text. When the text is present, writers can better identify important points, condense information, and clarify inconsistencies. Various devices, such as introductory statements and topic sentences, are used by authors to emphasize importance. However, relying too much on the text can lead to students copying directly instead of using their own words, especially for ESL students. Allowing students to refer to the text while summarizing can provide them with more mental space for selection and condensation. Typically, texts are presented during summarization tasks in academic settings to facilitate the process.

B. The characteristics of that text. The characteristics of the original text significantly impact the process of summarization. Three key characteristics—length, complexity, and text type—play a crucial role in this process. Shorter texts

make it easier to identify main ideas and select relevant information, whereas longer texts require more effort in condensing and selecting due to the abundance of ideas. Text complexity, including factors like vocabulary difficulty and sentence structure complexity, also affects summarization. More complex texts necessitate more judgments in deciding which ideas to include and require more transformations of the original ideas. Research suggests that when faced with complex texts, writers tend to adopt a paragraph-by-paragraph strategy rather than reorganizing and synthesizing the entire text.

Summary writing has numerous advantages for understanding reading passages. It helps learners grasp main ideas more deeply by encouraging them to condense information. Additionally, it assists in remembering important concepts by synthesizing information from the passage. Summarizing allows learners to concentrate on crucial details, which improves comprehension and prevents them from getting distracted by minor points. Moreover, summary writing enhances critical thinking skills as learners analyze and evaluate content, improving their ability to identify key points. It also helps in refining writing skills by encouraging clear and concise expression of ideas. Furthermore, summary writing prepares learners for assessments that require concise summaries and helps in language learning by providing practice in comprehension and expression. Thus, summary writing is a valuable strategy for improving comprehension, critical thinking, writing skills, and assessment preparation, while also aiding in language acquisition.

In conclusion, summarizing serves as a fundamental cognitive reading strategy in second language acquisition, offering several advantages for comprehending reading passages. Effective comprehension is essential for students, and employing various strategies, including summarizing, is key to achieving this. Summarizing allows learners to identify and condense main ideas, leading to a deeper engagement with the text and enhancing understanding. It also aids in retaining key concepts by synthesizing information from the passage and helps learners focus on essential information, preventing distraction by minor details. Furthermore, summarizing fosters critical thinking skills as learners analyze and evaluate content, improving their ability to discern important points. Additionally, it contributes to improving writing skills by promoting clear and concise expression of ideas. Moreover, summarizing prepares learners for assessments that require concise summaries and facilitates language learning by providing practice in comprehension and expression. Overall, summarizing emerges as a valuable strategy

for enhancing comprehension, critical thinking, writing abilities, assessment preparation, and language acquisition in second language acquisition contexts.

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